

HORIZON 2020

Coordination and Support Action

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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable No. D 4.1

EU-PolarNet website set up

Submission of Deliverable

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Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – CNRS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 - NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - CNR-DTA, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – IPEV, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - IGOT-UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – RUG, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – MINECO, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CSIC, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - UW-APRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – GEUS, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – VUB, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – RBINS, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - IGF PAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 - IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 - GINR
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EU-PolarNet website set up

The EU-PolarNet website has been officially launched on 19th May 2015. The address is www.eu-polarnet.eu